

Title

No phases? No phase separation

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Available: 25 September 2025

Main

ARISING FROM S.A. Shelby et al. *Nature Chemical Biology*

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41589-023-01268-8> (2023)

Phase separation has been a popular framework for interpreting molecular organization in membranes since the 1970s¹⁻³. However, it is typically invoked without evidence for phase coexistence. In a recent article, Shelby *et al.* present a correlation between B cell receptor (BCR) colocalization with fluorescent probes in live-cell and *in vitro* systems, which they state “directly and conclusively establishes phase separation as a functional organizing principle in cell plasma membranes”⁴. This verdict assumes causation from correlation while neglecting simpler explanations. The rationale for comparing isolated vesicles with live cells is precisely that phase separation is not directly observed in the latter. If the authors argue that phases are routinely induced by BCR clusters in live cells, as might be tentatively inferred from the paper’s title, conclusions, and illustrations, they are contradicting the well-documented idea that membrane proteins are surrounded by heterogeneous lipid distributions⁵.

In equilibrium, phase separation has a specific definition: it requires the formation of phases. Phases are homogeneous regions, characterized by intensive properties such as density that are consistent over the length of the region when averaged over time⁶. Although live cells are far-from-equilibrium systems, Shelby *et al.* clearly invoke “phase separation” in this context as a mechanistic extension of equilibrium phase separation. Their Figure 5 depicts time-averaged lipid distributions that are homogeneous, and their graphical abstract juxtaposes BCR cluster zones in live cells with artificially induced phases⁴. They assert that BCR cluster zones differ from phases in isolated vesicles by their level of contrast and regulatory control, but not by their homogeneity. They also hypothesize that components are sorted in live cells based on their binary phase preferences. Furthermore, Shelby and Veatch discuss and depict genuine phases around membrane proteins in two papers that seem to build the same hypothesis^{7,8} (Figure 1). Despite this, they state “Near, but not at, phase separation, extended domains... can assemble or disassemble”⁴. However, this statement likely refers to macro-scale or membrane-wide phase separation; a meaning which Shelby and Veatch use elsewhere⁷ (Figure 1c), lest they contradict their title “Membrane phase separation drives...”

and repeated assertions that phase separation is the organizing principle in live cells⁴. Overall, Shelby *et al* suggest to the reader that BCR clusters are surrounded by true phases or would-be phases under equilibrium conditions, although their use of personalised definitions makes some details of their hypothesis ambiguous.

Figure 1. Shelby and Veatch illustrate phases around protein clusters in figures from three articles^{4,7,8}, with this one from⁷. **a**, Membrane without proteins, depicted as a single phase. **b**, Membrane with protein clusters, which appear to induce phases. **c**, The contrast of phases around protein clusters is hypothesized to depend on the phase preference of the clustered proteins and the nearness of the membrane to large-scale phase separation. Used with permission from Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press⁷.

The data presented by Shelby *et al* are insufficient to support the conclusion that BCR clusters are surrounded by phases, or that some other transition resembling spinodal decomposition is responsible for organizing components in live cells⁴. The study shows that common sets of components tend to be near each other in two different systems, as evidenced by a linear correlation. It does not follow that a particular type of transition is a common mechanism between the two systems. Emergent phenomena such as phase separation and phase preferences depend on the overall composition and thermodynamic state of the system and are therefore not preserved. As a case in point, the phase partitioning efficacy of fluorescent constructs like the ones used in this study are notoriously difficult to reproduce, causing confusion among their users⁹. Overall, the assumption that the statistical organization

of the “probes” used by Shelby *et al* indicates an unseen ordered phase or spinodal decomposition-like transition around BCR clusters is poorly justified.

Figure 2. Lipid fingerprints from molecular dynamics simulations⁵. **a**, Two-dimensional maps showing density from three lipid classes, with notable heterogeneity indicated with arrows (I-V). **b**, Thickness, mean curvature, and Gaussian curvature. Used with permission from the American Chemical Society (ACS)⁵ (<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acscentsci.8b00143>). Further permissions related to the material excerpted should be directed to the ACS.

Structural biology and molecular dynamics simulations have revealed that proteins are surrounded by heterogeneous lipid distributions called fingerprints (Figure 2)⁵. Fingerprints often include extraordinary headgroup and aliphatic chain specificity¹⁰, networks of miscellaneous lipids extending from protein surfaces¹¹, and nonspecific or transient binding with spatial precision⁵. Such patterns are expected, as direct and indirect protein binding sites exhibit different lipid preferences. This heterogeneity is incompatible with the idea that the lipid distributions around protein clusters simply interpolate between binary phases (Figure 1c). Instead, these distributions are unique, emergent, and reflect an immense proteolipid code¹².

Competing interests

TAK has no competing interests to declare.

Author Contributions

TAK: conceptualization, writing.

Funding

This work was funded by a Clarendon Fund Scholarship in partnership with a Nuffield Department of Clinical Medicine Studentship and a Magdalen College Graduate Scholarship to TAK.

Acknowledgements

I thank Michael Overduin for discussions.

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